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INTRODUCTION OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP EDUCATION IN PUBLIC SECONDARY GENERAL SCHOOLS IN CAMEROON

Fritz Ikome Ngale Lyonga (Ph.D)

ORCID: 0000-0002-6604-1134

Department of Science of Education Higher Technical Teacher Training College, University of Buea, Cameroon

Corresponding author: fritz.ikome@ubuea.cm

Abstract

Entrepreneurship education is a recent field in education. From a field mainly related to small business, it is extended towards the enhancement of students' entrepreneurial attitudes and skills. This is mainly because of the complaints by employers in Cameroon that students who pass through the secondary general curriculum do not often possess the skills required by industries (Ndille, 2016). It can support students in developing an independent and versatile mind. By growing the spirit of entrepreneurship they will be able to solve local problems and at the same time make a decent living in the process and by so doing help generate decent employment for themselves and others. Developing entrepreneurship competence among students requires the mastery of concepts by teachers and the political will by administrators (Solomon, 2007). This study was a descriptive survey research, designed to analyse the Introduction of Entrepreneurship Education in Public Secondary general Schools in Cameroon. This study worked with 100 respondents. These respondents will comprise of 20 school administrators and 80 teachers from public secondary general schools. This study had the following objectives: If secondary school teachers have had any training in entrepreneurship education, again what are the convictions of teachers towards implementing entrepreneurship education in secondary schools and finally what they might think will hinder the implementation of entrepreneurship education in secondary schools. This study found out that: Most teachers and school administrators have had no training in entrepreneurial education. Again despite the lack of training most of the teachers and school administrators are convinced that entrepreneurship education will improve on their students survival abilities. And finally most of the respondents identified hindrances to the implementation of entrepreneurship education in secondary schools.

Keywords:

Entrepreneurship Education, Public Secondary General Schools in Cameroon

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Introduction

The key to establishing a culture of entrepreneurship in Cameroon is education, which depends on all the stakeholders, including state, educators, and learners themselves (Ndille, 2016). Entrepreneurship education has become very important for emerging nations. Cameroon as a country needs a transformative economy and education should take a front role in kick starting that. Mattay 2004 assumes entrepreneurship is a way out for declining economies and stagnating ones. Entrepreneurship education (EE) service provision has a perceived role as a catalyst for human capital and socio-economic development in Africa (Anosike, Kolade, Ahmed 2017). Entrepreneurship education has the mandate to equip the youth with functional knowledge and skill to build up their character, attitude and vision. It has a vital role in developing eco-system that promotes innovation (European Union, 2006). Entrepreneurship is crucial for socio-economic development because it creates a lot of opportunities that boost economies. Entrepreneurship education will go a long way to equip individuals with self-employment capabilities, skills and intentions. Entrepreneurship education must be a part of secondary school curriculum in Cameroon. This was reiterated by the Minister of Secondary Education Prof. Nalova Lyonga in Kribi on the 27/3/2021 while chairing the official launch of the Open Door and Entrepreneurial day of technical education in Cameroon.

Secondary education is a very important phase of education for the learner in terms of knowledge development and acquisition of skills (Tambo 2010). It is there for paramount to ensure that secondary schools provide learners with real world skills and knowledge. So that they as citizens can contribute to economic growth of the country. This can be greatly achieved if entrepreneurship education is taught at the secondary schools level.

There are many challenges facing secondary schools education in Cameroon (Ndille, 2017). Despite many advances and gains made since independence the system still produces and reproduces a lot of inequalities to jobs and better life. There is great belief that if entrepreneurship programs are taught to all secondary students, they would be of great value to the country. That is why this paper seeks to bring out the awareness for entrepreneurship education to be taught in secondary schools and its advantage to the learners and the country as a whole.

Justification/Problem

According to the World Bank Report of 2021, unemployment stands at 3.87% with an increase of 0.3% from 2020. So since 1999 unemployment in the country Cameroon has been facing a steady increase. Again the acceleration growth in GDP experienced by Cameroon between 2011 through 2018 was not sustainable (World Bank Report 2016). This was because it relied solely on the ambitious public investment projects and not enough private sector led growth (WB Report 2016). Public debt increased to about 30% of GDP and poverty rates have not decreased.

The rural regions of the Far North and the North have poverty levels of 72%, where as in urban areas poverty is at 4.8%. According to the World Bank Report 2016 Cameroon has not met any of its Millennium Development Goal (MDG) with the exception of primary school enrollment. The issues confronting the nation going from high rate of unemployment, youth and graduate unemployment; overdependence on outside products and innovation; Low financial development and advancement; among others (World Bank Report 2016). Based on the above issues plaguing the Cameroonian economy, this study wants to investigate entrepreneurship education in secondary schools as a catalyst to providing sustainable solutions to the above issues. This study is in line with the World Bank's Education Sector Strategy 2020, "Learning for All: Investing in People's Knowledge and Skills to Promote Development" (World Bank 2011).

Research Objectives

It has the following as research objectives:

- a) To find out if teachers and school administrators have any idea/training in entrepreneurship education.
- b) To understand the beliefs and convictions of teachers and school administrators in relation to implementing entrepreneurship education in secondary schools.
- c) To find out according to teachers and school administrators the hindrance they think will affect the successful implementation of entrepreneurship education in secondary schools.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Human Capital Theory

"Human capital" can be defined as knowledge, skills, attitudes, aptitudes, and other acquired traits contributing to production (Goode 1959). The Human Capital Theory belongs to the bigger research programme of orthodox or neoclassic economics (Zamora 2007). Human capital theory rests on the assumption that formal education is highly instrumental and necessary to improve the productive capacity of a population. In short, human capital theorists argue that an educated population is a productive population. Human capital theory emphasizes how education increases the productivity and efficiency of workers by increasing the level of cognitive stock of economically productive human capability, which is a product of innate abilities and investment in human beings (Woodhall, 1997).

The first writings on human capital comes from the 18th century Scottish economist, Adam Smith. Adam Smith in *The Wealth of Nations* (Smith, 1776) set the stage for the study of human capital. Although he does not use the phrase human capital, he identifies the acquired and useful abilities of individuals as a fundamental source of wealth and economic progress of a country. But, the American economist, Greg Becker (1960), was arguably the biggest pioneer for the human capital theory. In his works in economic sciences notably in *Human Capital: A Theoretical and Empirical Analysis, with Special Reference to Education*, he coined the idea of investing in people. He pointed out that education and training were investments that could add to productivity. This was very important at that time as the world accumulated more and more physical capital, the opportunity cost of going to school declined. Education became an increasingly important component of the workforce. The term was also adopted by corporate finance and became part of intellectual capital, and more broadly as human capital.

The Human Capital Theory inherits the basic metaphysical assumptions from the 'hard core' of the Orthodox Economics Research Programme. The basic assumptions in simple terms: We invest in the physical means of our business, like machinery or technology. This allows us to produce our stocks or products; and profit from it. So, we should invest in human capital the same way – through education and training. Investing in human capital allows you to see growth measured through your staff's abilities, values, and skillset. This will increase business productivity, and in time, revenue, and brand-name.

This theory takes center stage in this paper because if we glamour for Cameroonian youths to be entrepreneurs or be self-employed, there is no better way than educating youths and students by incorporating entrepreneurship in their learning programs. Against a common conception according to Gartner (1990) that entrepreneurship is only for entrepreneurial individuals creating innovative organizations that grow and create value, either for the purpose of profit. We should educate our students on the art of entrepreneurship.

Entrepreneurship education

It is important to understand at this stage what the author understands by entrepreneurship education, and indicate the differences that exist between the often confused areas of education and training. Enterprise education is the process or series of activities which aims to enable an individual to assimilate and develop knowledge, skills, values and understanding that are not simply related to a narrow field of activity, but which allow a broad range of problems to be defined, analyzed and solved (Garavan, T., Costine, P. and Heraty, 1995). Nowadays, entrepreneurship education (EE) is one of the fastest growing fields of education globally (Solomon, 2007). It is concerned with learning processes that prepares learners to be responsible and enterprising individuals. It helps people develop the skills, knowledge, and attitudes necessary to achieve the goals they set out for themselves. Entrepreneurship education is based on research indicating that some entrepreneurial behaviors can be taught and learned, starting in youth and culminating in their young adult or adult years or when they are potential or practicing entrepreneurs (Hegarty 2006; Souitaris, Zerbini, and Al-Laham 2007; Walter and Dohse 2009). Evidence by Heinonen and Poikkijoki (2006) shows that people with entrepreneurial education are more employable. Entrepreneurship education pursues the development on students the knowledge, skills and motivation to encourage entrepreneurial success in a diversity of settings. Each level of education, from primary school until graduate university level variations of entrepreneurship education are offered since the competences and abilities to be developed are in tune with the main pedagogical goals to be pursued in each age and maturity level of education.

Entrepreneurship education has evolved over time despite global interest, the body of available research remains limited, and what exists to date tends to be methodologically weak (Glaub and Frese 2011). According to Sirelkhathim (2015), the 1980s much Entrepreneurship Education literature discussed the trend of the increasing number of Entrepreneurship Education programs in universities (McMullan & Vesper, 1987). Over time, the focus moved towards the actual process and content of Entrepreneurship Educational programs (Vesper & Gartner, 1997). Moreover, more recent works take a rigorous look at course content (DeTienne & Chandler, 2004; Fiet, 2001; Honig, 2004; Shepherd, 2004). Other recent articles about entrepreneurial learning, are making a serious attempt to merge theory, practice and actual observation of what entrepreneurs do and how they learn and how that can be incorporated into Entrepreneurship Educational programs (Harmeling & Sarasvathy, 2013).

Point should be noted that Entrepreneurship Educational programs might be affected by country-specific issues. Samwel Mwasalwiba, (2010), believe that the overall objectives of these Entrepreneurship Educational programs are universal. This article will take advantage of this diversity to map out common and best practices to teach Entrepreneurship Educational programs in our secondary schools in Cameroon. Moreover, whilst many articles have studied Entrepreneurship Educational provision at the undergraduate level, far fewer have focused on the secondary school level.

In the European Union the currently accepted and implemented model of entrepreneurship education is based on Heinonen and Poikkijoki (2006) that has the main objective to provide students with the attitudes, knowledge and skills for entrepreneurial action, having the different dimensions of education for entrepreneurship to be deployed in multiple categories, which constitute the framework of the various learning outcomes implemented and achieved by the countries of the European Union.

Entrepreneurship education basically focuses on creation of entrepreneurial culture. It helps potential entrepreneurs to identify and pursue opportunities. It is not limited to boosting start-ups, innovative ventures and new jobs. Entrepreneurship is a competency for all, helping young people to become creative and self confident in whatever they undertake. The basic characteristics and importance of entrepreneurship education as a discipline as obtained from the critical review of the works related to it have been identified by the authors as follows : It is a function of innovation (Contillon, 1931 and Kirby, 2004). Also it is a function of fostering leadership (Kuratka & Harnsby, 1996). Vesper & William, 1997 stated that it is an organizational building function and a function of high achievement. Also it involves creation and operation of an enterprise (Kuratka & Jennings, 1999).

It is process of creating value for customers by exploiting untapped opportunities (McGrath, MacMillan & Scheinberg, 1992). More so It is strong and positive orientation towards growth in wealth, knowledge and employment (Robert, 1998). And finally it is concerned with attitudinal change, risk taking abilities and turning ideas in to actions (Gunday & Kickal, 1998). Thus as a discipline entrepreneurship education always tries to inculcate some skill, so that one can play a role of catalyst for socio-economical change. It gives force to shape the future society and one's own life simultaneously.

It is also important to know how to carry out the teaching of entrepreneurship in secondary schools. Going about it one needs to understand the competencies that students will gain throughout the program. Generally, competencies include knowledge, skills, attitudes and behaviors needed to complete an activity successfully (Morris et al., 2013; Sánchez, 2013). Regarding more specific competencies, they include, amongst many others: opportunity recognition, opportunity assessment, risk management, creative problem solving, value creation and building, and using networks (Morris et al., 2013). Entrepreneurial education focuses on exploring how entrepreneurs gain the previously mentioned entrepreneurial competencies (Cope, 2005).

Based on the above competencies, entrepreneurial researchers agree that, Entrepreneurship Education is centered on the idea of gaining entrepreneurial competencies through experience that entrepreneurs gain from “learning by doing” (Cope & Watts, 2000), routinized activities (Reuber and Fischer, 1993 and Cope, 2005), contingencies, non-continuous events (Harmeling & Sarasvathy, 2013), failure (Minniti & Bygrave, 2001), and reflecting (Cope, 2005) from experience gained through these life events. Researchers commonly agree that teaching Entrepreneurship Education should follow these teaching methods; the three teaching themes of pro-Entrepreneurship Education vision are: theoretical-oriented courses that teach (1) “about” entrepreneurship (Piperopoulos & Dimov, 2014).

Here the aim is to increase awareness about entrepreneurship, encourage students to choose entrepreneurship as a potential career choice (Fayolle & Gailly, 2013) and consider self-employment (Klapper & Tegtmeier, 2010); and practical-oriented courses that teach (2) “for” entrepreneurship (Piperopoulos & Dimov, 2014) aims to encourage students and enhance their intentions to be entrepreneurs in future and (3) “through” entrepreneurship, which aim to graduate entrepreneurs (Vincett & Farlow, 2008), support new venture creation (Lundqvist & Williams Middleton, 2013) and develop entrepreneurial competencies (Bridge, Hegarty, & Porter, 2010). Thus along the course of this paper one will be able to say which themes should be used in secondary schools.

According to the Directorate-General for Enterprise and Industry European Commission 2012, an entrepreneurial teacher is more of a coach than someone who lectures. They support the individual learning processes of students and the development of personal competences. The current thinking on entrepreneurial teaching is based on a number of recurring themes. Entrepreneurship education is more than preparation on how to run a business. It is about how to develop the entrepreneurial attitudes, skills and knowledge which, in short, should enable a student to ‘turn ideas into action’. Teachers cannot teach how to be entrepreneurial without themselves being entrepreneurial.

Entrepreneurial competences require active methods of engaging students to release their creativity and innovation. Entrepreneurial competency and skills can be acquired or built only through hands-on, real life learning experiences. Entrepreneurial skills can be taught across all subjects as well as a separate subject. Entrepreneurship education should focus on ‘intrapreneurs’ as well as entrepreneurs, in light of the fact that most students will use entrepreneurial skills within companies or public institutions. To give entrepreneurship education real traction, there is a need to develop learning outcomes related to entrepreneurship, and related assessment methods and quality assurance procedures for all levels of education. These should be designed to help teachers progress in the acquisition of entrepreneurial knowledge, skills and attitudes. The entrepreneurship education agenda

should be promoted beyond teacher education institutions to businesses and the wider community. Teachers and schools will not be able to realise their ambitions without cooperation and partnerships with colleagues, businesses and other stakeholders.

Secondary Education

At independence, Cameroon inherited two educational systems; a Francophone subsystem in the mandated East Cameroon in 1960 and an Anglo-Saxon sub system; in the mandated Anglophone West Cameroon in 1961(Alemnge, 2021).In order to improve the life of young Cameroonians the governments of East Cameroon and West Cameroon passed an educational law in 1963 whose implementation should have resulted in a harmonized secondary school programme for the country (Alemnge, 2019). Due to many shortcomings especially with secondary schools basically reproducing candidates who depend on government for employment. The government organize a national Forum on Education in 1995 to which all stake holders were invited and charged with the responsibility to make proposals to government for the long-awaited reforms.

The Forum met and made proposals to government addressing all aspects of the education. The recommendations proposed by the Forum were exploited and led to the publication of the National Education Policy, encapsulated in the Law of 1998 to lay down guidelines for Education in Cameroon (Ndille 2021).According to Alemnge(2021), the long awaited reform leading to the new and harmonized secondary schools' syllabi found expression within the general reform movement (GESP, 2010) aimed at transforming the national economy from producing and commercializing primary products to an emergent one by 2035 that will add value to its products by transforming them into finished product before sale.

Therefore, the new syllabi are guided by the desire to produce the human resources that will be equipped, with the required skills, knowledge, attitudes and creativity to be able to transform the society to achieve emergence by 2035 (GESP, 2010).This is where entrepreneurship education comes in, becauseit is a strong and positive orientation towards growth in wealth, knowledge and employment (Robert, 1998). Sad to notice entrepreneurship education was not included in the new syllabi.

There are two types of secondary education in Cameroon: general secondary education and technical secondary education. Generalsecondary education in both subsystems (The English sub system and the French sub system) admission to the first cycle is by competitive examination and the legal age is thirteen in theEnglish sub-system and twelve in the French sub-system. If in the French sub-system theobtaining of the BEPC is the fruit of four years of study, on the other hand in the English sub-system, it is at the end of five years that one obtains the General Certificate of EducationOrdinary / Level (GCEO / L).As for the second cycle, the age indicated is sixteen in the French sub-system and seventeenin the English sub-system. In each of its subsystems, the duration of the studies for the GCE A/L and BAC is respectively two years and three years. Technical secondary educationincludes two cycles:The first cycle lasts four years and is sanctioned by the Certificate of Professional Aptitude (CAP).The second cycle opens its doors to the holders of the CAP and the BEPC. The duration ofstudies is three years culminating in the awarding of the Technician's Baccalaureate or aTechnician's Certificate or the General Certificate of Advanced Level Education which givesaccess to higher education or active life?

Research Methodology

This research will be a descriptive survey research. This study worked with 100 respondents. These respondents will comprise of 20 school administrators and 80 teachers from public secondary general schools. Public secondary general schools will be used because they act as pace setters and majority of students in respective communities in Cameroon attend this schools. Secondary General Education is used here to refer to the secondary level of education that focuses on General Education subjects; the curriculum comprising subjects like Mathematics,Physics, Chemistry, Biology, History, Geography, Literature, English and French as opposed to Secondary Technical, Vocational or

Commercial Education which focuses on training to fit into particular trades (Tambo, 2003). Information will be gotten through the use of Likert scale questionnaires and interviews and these data will be collected based on the research objectives and analysed descriptively using simple percentages and key concepts/themes, groundings, sampled quotation, frequencies and percentages. The major introductive variables investigated in this study included training, conviction, and hindrances to the introduction of entrepreneurial education in public general schools.

Again the researchers did a systematic literature review (SLR) to help review the literature in a transparent and clear way on the ways entrepreneurship education can be thought in Cameroon secondary schools and its importance to secondary school leavers and the entire Cameroonian economy. This method is characterized by transparency, clarity, equality and accessibility, unified and focused (Thorpe, Holt, Pittaway, & Macpherson, 2006).

Secondary General Education is used here to refer to the secondary level of education, that focuses on General Education subjects; the curriculum comprising subjects like Mathematic, Physics, Chemistry, Biology, History, Geography, Literature, English and French as opposed to Secondary Technical, Vocational or Commercial Education which focuses on training to fit into particular trades (Tambo, 2003).

Findings and Discussions

The respondents were all secondary school administrators and teachers making up of 8 principals, 9 vice-principals, 3 deans of studies and 80 teachers. Below are the following reactions when respondents were asked the respective research questions:

When respondents were asked if they had any training in entrepreneurship education, about 78% of the respondents said they did not have any training in entrepreneurship education. That is about 78% of them did not have any idea while only 22% of them said they have some sort of training in entrepreneurship education. Yang (2016) noticed that entrepreneurship education is lacking behind in most American cities because of lack of knowledge and training of most school administrators and teachers. Thus in our Cameroon situation when a majority of respondents (school administrators and teachers) lack the training about Entrepreneurship education, there will be thus limited action towards implementing it in our secondary schools. Since most administrators and teachers do not know about Entrepreneurship education it thus makes it difficult to be implemented in our secondary schools. This is a very important reason why entrepreneurship education is not being thought in our secondary schools. Most of them lack the training in entrepreneurship education and how to teach it. According to Birdthistle et al. (2007) and Frank (2007), when the educational system lacks enterprise-related teacher training, then teachers will not have any idea and knowledge about entrepreneurship education.

Thus making it difficult for implementation. However the above study claims that Entrepreneurship Education training has a positive effect on Entrepreneurship Education training and practice in secondary schools. It will be paramount if Entrepreneurship Education training is introduced in our teacher training colleges in Cameroon. This view is also supported by Bennett's (2006)-study which claim that, teacher training played a significant role and it increases the number of practices applied to entrepreneurship education. Deakins et al. (2005), reported that they view changes specifically in head teachers' attitudes and practices after an enterprise-related leadership program. They identified development in entrepreneurship practices as such, in practices involving their staff, students, and parents in their respective schools.

Therefore, this study has suggested the following propositions: **Proposition I:** Because many head teachers and teachers have had no training in entrepreneurship education and practice, short Enterprise-related training programs and seminars be introduced to teachers and head-teaches. This will go a long way to positively affects head-teachers 'and teachers ' entrepreneurship education practices in secondary schools. **Proposition II:** It will be paramount if Entrepreneurship Education training and practice is introduced in our teacher training colleges in Cameroon, where designing a

curriculum for entrepreneurship Education and techniques in teaching will be taught to teachers and school administrators.

The conviction of school administrators and teachers was also examined. This was when respondents were asked if they believe entrepreneurship education should be taught in secondary schools in Cameroon. Sah & Shah (2020) emphasized on the importance of beliefs and conviction in guiding teaching practices, and Tatto (1998) emphasized on the importance of identifying teacher's beliefs related to his/her teaching; It is very necessary to verify teacher's beliefs and how these beliefs influence his/her teaching practices and his/her roles for developing their instructional behaviour. Studying teachers' beliefs helps them to build their classroom activities and practices and identify the strengths and weaknesses in teaching, and then develop their teaching performance (Sah and Shah, 2020; Kutáľková, 2017; Aksoy, 2015).

So when asked about 62 of the respondents said they believe entrepreneurship education should be taught in secondary schools. That is 62% of them where for the fact that entrepreneurship education will improve on the capacity of our students. Meanwhile 38 of the respondent that is 38% did not believe that entrepreneurship education was necessary for students in secondary schools. When asked for their reasons they offered a good number. Top on the agenda was that secondary students already have a lot of courses on their syllabus, and no course can be removed for Entrepreneurship Education to take its place. So adding entrepreneurship education to their scheme will be too much for the students. Another recurrent response was that teachers do not have the content materials to teach. The above two concerns can easily be attended too. Subsequent studies will be dedicated to address them. This leads to the third question asked to respondents.

They were asked what hindrances do they feel will prevent the successful implementation of entrepreneurship education. Challenges that came up where lack of equipment, insufficient funds, lack of teaching content materials and lack of properly trained teachers. Surprisingly they also mentioned the lack of motivation. All these were identified in the course of implementing entrepreneurship education in their respective secondary schools.

Table 1

SN	RESPONCES	NUMBER	PERCENTAGE
1	Teachers are not trained	40	40%
2	Lack of teaching materials	22	22%
3	Too much teaching load	16	16%
4	Insufficient funds	14	14%
5	poorly motivated teachers	8	8%
Total		100	100%

Title: Hindrances to implementing entrepreneurship education in secondary schools.

(Source: field work)

From the above table a majority of respondents said that the major hindrance to the implementation of entrepreneurship education in secondary schools is that many teachers are not trained. This was noted earlier when Yang (2016) noticed that entrepreneurship education is lacking behind in most American cites because of lack of knowledge of most school administrators and teachers. This is a problem because as Orji (2011) explained, the entrepreneurship curriculum will have to promote occupational aspirations and job readiness, Hand-on & Work-based experiences and Acquisition of functional organizational skills. He wonder if these dreams will be actualize without trained and qualified teachers in school who will be able to bring that out the above aspirations in students. So if our Cameroonian teachers lack the training they will not be able to deliver so that the objectives be achieved. There for **Proposition II** becomes very urgent in order for the country to achieve the successful implementation of entrepreneurship education in most of our secondary schools.

Conclusion

Therefore, education at secondary and tertiary levels should prepare its graduates for the rapidly changing world. For least developed countries like Malawi, they need to create a labor force for existing and new innovative labor markets are enormous. Thus, providing a type of education that develops entrepreneurial competencies in its students is paramount. Most youth at that education level would be more interested in entrepreneurial studies with a definitive purpose because of their practical nature. Youths with enthusiasm, motivation, risk-taking, flexibility, energy, resourcefulness, and willingness to try new things are an excellent target for entrepreneurial education. Hence, most secondary school students are more likely to embrace entrepreneurship as a subject of study. The education system needs to be reformed to meet the needs of upcoming job markets. This study asks the most important players of an educational system what must be done to guarantee future graduates high-quality entrepreneurial skills.

References

- Afe, A.J (2014) Entrepreneurship Education: A panacea for Unemployment, Poverty Reduction and National Insecurity in Developing and Underdeveloped Countries. *American Journal of Contemporary Research*, 4(3) 124.
- Andrew Yang (1996) Why Entrepreneurship Education Does Not Work: *Journal of Enterprising Culture*
- Burgoyne, J. 1989. Creating The Managerial Portfolio: Building On Competency Approaches To Management Development. *Management Learning*, 20, 56-61.
- Clark, B. et al. (1984). Do Courses in Entrepreneurship Aid in New Venture Creation? *Journal of Small Business Management*, 22(2), 25-31.
- Dana, L. (1995). Entrepreneurship in a Remote sub-Arctic community. *Entrepreneurship: Theory & Practice*, 20(1), 57-72
- Dionco-Adetayo, E.A. (2003). Factors Influencing Attitude of Youth Towards Entrepreneurship Program.
- Donckels, R. (1991). Education and Entrepreneurship Experiences from Secondary and University Education in Belgium. *Journal of Small Business & Entrepreneurship*, 9(1), 35-42.
- Drucker, P. E. (1985). *Innovation and Entrepreneurship*. New York: Harper & Row.
- Echtner, C. (1995). Entrepreneurial Training in Developing Countries. *Annals of Tourism Research*, 22(1), 119-134.
- Fayolle, A. (2002). Exploratory Study to Assess the Effects of Entrepreneurship Program on French Student Entrepreneurial Behaviors. *Journal of Enterprising Culture*, 8(2), 168- 184.
- Fayolle, A. (2005). "Evaluation of Entrepreneurship Education: Behavior Performing Or Intention Increasing?". *International Journal of Entrepreneurship and Small Business* 2(1), 89–98
- Fayolle, A., & Gailly, B. (2009). "Assessing the Impact of Entrepreneurship Education: A Methodology and Three Experiments from French Engineering Schools," in *Handbook of University-Wide Entrepreneurship Education*. Eds. G. P. West III, E. J. Gatewood and K. G. Shaver. Cheltenham, UK: Edward Elgar, 203–214.
- Fisher, S., Graham, M. & Compeau, M. 2008. Starting from Scratch: Understanding the Learning Outcomes of Undergraduate Entrepreneurship Education. In: Harrison, R. T. & Leitch, C. (eds.) *Entrepreneurial Learning: Conceptual Frameworks and Applications*. New York, NY: Routledge.
- Gary S. Becker. "Human Capital: A Theoretical and Empirical Analysis, with Special Reference to Education." National Bureau of Economic Research, 1975.
- Gibb, A. 2002. In Pursuit of a New 'Enterprise' And 'Entrepreneurship' Paradigm for Learning: Creative Destruction, New Values, New Ways of Doing Things and New Combinations of Knowledge. *International Journal of Management*.
- Heinonen, J. & Hytti, U. 2010. Back to Basics: The Role of Teaching in Developing The Entrepreneurial University. *The International Journal of Entrepreneurship and Innovation*, 11, 283-292.
- Hermann, F., Korunka, C., Lueger, M., and Mugler, J. (2005). Entrepreneurial Orientation and Education in Austrian Secondary Schools. *Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development*, 12 (2), 259-273.
- Hytti, U. & O'gorman, C. 2004. What is Enterprise Education? An Analysis of the Objectives and Methods of Enterprise Education Programs in Four European Countries. *Education+ Training*, 46, 11-23
- Hytti, U. (2000). Is Entrepreneurship A Disease That Can Be Taught Via the Internet? An Interim Evaluation of The Distance Education Program of Entrepreneurship in Finish Upper Secondary School Level. Accessed on May 20, 2021, http://www.tukkk.fi/pki/julkaisut/konferenssit/is_Entrepreneurship_a.pdf
- Hytti, U. 2005. New Meanings for Entrepreneurs: From Risk-taking Heroes to Safeseeking Professionals. *Journal of Organizational Change Management*, 18, 594-611.
- Johnson, C. 1988. Enterprise Education and Training. *British Journal of Education and Work*, 2, 61-65
- Kiggubdu, M. N. (2002). Entrepreneurs and Entrepreneurship in Africa: What Is Known and What Needs to be Done. *Journal of Developmental Entrepreneurship*, 7(3).

- Kolvareid, L. & Moen, O. (1997). Entrepreneurship Among Business Graduates: Does A Major in Entrepreneurship Make A Difference? *Journal of European Industrial Training*, 21(4), 154-160.
- Kraiger, K., Ford, J. K. & Salas, E. 1993. Application of Cognitive, Skill-Based, and Affective Theories of Learning Outcomes to New Methods of Training Evaluation. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 78, 311-328
- Kyrö, P. 2005. Entrepreneurial Learning in A Cross-Cultural Context Challenges Previous Learning Paradigms. In: Kyrö, P. & Carrier, C. (eds.) *The Dynamics of Learning Entrepreneurship in a Cross-Cultural University Context*. Hämeenlinna: University of Tampere.
- Lackeus, M. (2015). "Entrepreneurship in Education: What, Why, When, How", *Entrepreneurship 360: Background Paper*.
- Mahieu, R. 2006. *Agents of Change and Policies of Scale: A Policy Study of Entrepreneurship and Enterprise in Education*. Doctoral Thesis, Umeå Universitet.
- Matlay, Harry. 2004. Entrepreneurship and Small e-business Development: Towards a Comparative Research Agenda. *Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development*.
- Moberg, K. 2014. *Assessing the Impact of Entrepreneurship Education - From ABC to Ph.D*. Doctoral Thesis, Copenhagen Business School.]
- Moberg, K. 2014. Two Approaches to Entrepreneurship Education: The Different Effects of Education for and Through Entrepreneurship at The Lower Secondary Level. *International Journal of Management Education*, In Press.
- Moberg, K., Stenberg, E. & Vestergaard, L. 2012. *Impact of Entrepreneurship Education in Denmark -2012*. Odense, Denmark: The Danish Foundation for Entrepreneurship –Young Enterprise.
- Morris, M. H. (2001). From the Editor: Entrepreneurship is Economic Development. *Journal of Developmental Entrepreneurship*, 6(3), v.
- Mwasalwiba, E. S. 2010. Entrepreneurship Education: A Review of Its Objectives, Teaching Methods, and Impact Indicators. *Education + Training*, 52 20-47.
- O'Connor, A. 2013. A Conceptual Framework for Entrepreneurship Education Policy: Meeting Government and Economic Purposes. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 28, 546-563.
- O'Connor, G. C. 2008. Major Innovation as a Dynamic Capability: A Systems Approach. *Journal of Product Innovation Management*, 25, 313-330.
- QAA2012. *Enterprise and Entrepreneurship Education: Guidance For UK Higher Education Providers*. Gloucester, UK: The Quality Assurance Agency for Higher Education.
- Redford, D., Marques, M., et al (2014). *Impact Assessment of Entrepreneurship Education in African Secondary Schools: An Evidence-based Case study of Success in Angola*, Platform for Entrepreneurship Education Portugal;
- Sánchez, J. (2013). "The Impact of an Entrepreneurship Education Program on Entrepreneurial Competencies and Intention". *Journal of Small Business Management*, 51: 447-465.
- Southon, M. & West, C. (2004). *Capitalism for Kids*. Director, 58(2), 27-28.
- Spinosa, C., Flores, F. & Dreyfus, H. L. 1999. *Disclosing New Worlds: Entrepreneurship, Democratic Action, and The Cultivation of Solidarity*, Cambridge, MA, MIT Press.
- The European Union (EU) (1999). *Action Plan to Promote Entrepreneurship and Competitiveness*.
- Tshikuku, K. (2004). *Culture, Entrepreneurship, and Development in Africa*. Proceeding from the International Conference on Cultural Approach to Development in Africa, Dakar, Senegal.
- Volkman, C., Wilson, K. E., Mariotti, S., Rabuzzi, D., Vyakarnam, S. & Sepulveda, A. 2009. *Educating the Next Wave of Entrepreneurs - Unlocking Entrepreneurial Capabilities to Meet the Global Challenges of the 21st Century*. Geneva: World Economic Forum
- Weligamage, S. S. (2009). *Graduates' Employability skills: Evidence from Literature Review*. Sri Lanka: University of Kelaniya. Accessed on May 20, 2021, <http://www.kln.ac.lk/uokr/ASAIHL/SubThemeA8.pdf>
- Wilson, F., J. Kickul, & D. Marlino (2007). "Gender, Entrepreneurial Self-Efficacy, and Entrepreneurial Career Intentions: Implications for Entrepreneurship Education". *Entrepreneurship: Theory and Practice*, 31(3), 387-406.
- Youniss, J., Bales, S., Christmas-Best, V., Diversi, M., McLaughlin, M. & Silb